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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Low back pain is a major factor causing productivity loss among occupational “musculoskeletal disorders” and is a significant global public health issue. In 2020, it accounted for 619 million cases worldwide, making it one of the leading causes of years lived with disability (YLD) and severely reducing quality of life (Carregaro et al., 2020; Ferreira et al., 2023). This study aimed to develop a tool to assess the impact of low back pain on work motivation, performance, and productivity, addressing the lack of such an instrument in the literature.

Materials and Methods: This methodological study focused on developing a scale. The sample included individuals aged 18 years or older, actively employed in various sectors, and presenting with low back pain at T.C. SB Hitit University Çorum Erol Olçok Training and Research Hospital’s Neurosurgery Clinic between February 1 and May 1, 2024. A 25-item pool was created based on a literature review and expert contributions. Five experts reviewed the items, and necessary revisions were made. A five-point Likert scale was used. Construct validity was assessed using exploratory (EFA) and confirmatory factor analyses (CFA), while criterion validity was tested through correlations with the Oswestry Disability Index (ODI) (Yakut et al., 2004). The cut-off value was determined via ROC analysis, based on ODI sensitivity and specificity.

Results: The study group (n=247) included 50.2% women (n=124), with a mean age of 37.49±9.45 years. The KMO value was 0.872, and Bartlett's test p-value was <0.001, confirming the suitability for factor analysis. EFA and internal consistency analyses indicated reliability, with five subfactors and a Cronbach's alpha of 0.890. The Guttman Split-Half coefficient was 0.789, demonstrating adequate reliability. A low-to-moderate positive correlation was found between the scale and ODI (r=+0.382; p<0.001). CFA results showed $\chi^2/df=389/160$, CFI=0.904, TLI=0.886, SRMR=0.0636, and RMSEA=0.076, indicating good fit. The ROC curve determined a cut-off score of 63.5 (Sensitivity: 78%, Specificity: 59%), with 43.3% of participants

experiencing productivity loss due to low back pain. The area under the curve was 72.2% ($p < 0.001$). Scores ranged from 20 to 100, with higher scores indicating greater negative impact. Scores of 63.5 or above reflected significant productivity impairment.

Conclusion: This scale is a valid and reliable tool for evaluating the impact of low back pain on work productivity. Clinicians can use it to consider workplace factors, helping to prevent productivity loss and mitigate broader health issues.

PEER REVIEW STATEMENT

This paper has undergone a double-blind peer review process and has been approved by the scientific committee of the conference.

KEYWORDS

Low back pain, work productivity, scale

CONFLICT OF INTEREST DECLARATION

There is no commercial, financial, or personal conflict of interest in this study.

REFERENCES

Carregaro, R. L., Tottoli, C. R., Rodrigues, D. D. S., Bosmans, J. E., da Silva, E. N., & van Tulder, M. (2020). Low back pain should be considered a health and research priority in Brazil: Lost productivity and healthcare costs between 2012 to 2016. *PLOS ONE*, *15*(4), e0230902.

<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0230902>

Ferreira, M. L., De Luca, K., Haile, L. M., Steinmetz, J. D., Culbreth, G. T., Cross, M., ... Mahmoodpoor, A. (2023). Global, regional, and national burden of low back pain, 1990–2020, its attributable risk factors, and projections to 2050: A systematic analysis of the Global Burden of Disease Study 2021. *The Lancet Rheumatology*, *5*(6), e316–e329. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2665-9913\(23\)00098-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2665-9913(23)00098-X)

Yakut, E., Düger, T., Öksüz, Ç., Yörükan, S., Üreten, K., Turan, D., ... Güler, Ç. (2004). Validation of the Turkish version of the Oswestry Disability Index for patients with low back pain. *Spine*, *29*(5), 581–585.

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